

NDAC/LO/017

1983 Feb 07

Error propagation formulae for Step 1 and 3

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1. Introduction

A slightly modified approach to the great-circle reduction (GCR) formula is described in this note. It is closer to the actual data reductions (as planned by NDAC) in that the abscissa mean errors, σ_a , refer to a complete set (12 h interval) rather than a single great-circle scan. The coefficients of improvement (COI) are also redefined as a consequence. An important consideration for the new formulae is how the "average" observing precision is most properly defined; this is discussed in Section 2. Section 3 gives a preliminary calibration of the set reduction formula by means of Copenhagen simulations. Results for the new COI are given in Section 4, and the last section contains an accuracy assessment based on these results and data (on the frame level) from MATRA's SDR reports (November 1982).

2. On the averaging of precision measures

Let σ_{ai} be the abscissa mean error (m.e. = standard deviation) of star number i as obtained in a set (or great-circle) solution. The m.e. is a function of the typical precision ($\sigma_{\eta i}$) of individual observations of the star, of the number (n_i) of such observations, of the overall precision and rigidity of the solution, and of a number of more or less unpredictable factors relating to the detailed structure of the observation equations. Neglecting the latter "accidental" factors, we write

$$\sigma_{ai} = f(\sigma_{\eta i}, n_i^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \langle \sigma_{\eta} \rangle, \langle n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle) \quad (1)$$

where $\langle \rangle$ denotes some suitable averaging over the different stars (e.g. the arithmetic, geometric, or harmonic mean). If all stars were observed with the same precision and the same number of times, any average would give the same result in (1). In reality there is however a large spread of values, ranging over more than a decade for $\sigma_{\eta i}$, in which case different averages are considerably different.

Question: is it possible to define the averaging operator in (1) such that the same formula applies, with reasonable approximation, to a wide variety of distributions of σ_{η_i} and n_i ? The answer is yes, and the proper average is the (unweighted) arithmetic mean. This conclusion is based on the simple experiments reported below.

For any $q \neq 0$ and any set of positive numbers x_j , $j = 1, 2, \dots, M$, we define the q -average as

$$\langle x \rangle_q := \left[M^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^M (x_j)^q \right]^{1/q} \quad q \neq 0, \quad x_j > 0 \quad (2)$$

$q = -1, 1$ and 2 gives, respectively, the harmonic mean, the arithmetic mean, and the rms value. By taking the limit it can be seen that $q = 0$ corresponds to the geometric mean. If the x 's are mean errors, then $q = -2$ gives a value with mean weight. Thus, the q -interval of interest here is roughly $|q| \leq 2$.

A "mini-set" comprising $N = 49$ stars (abscissae a_i , $i = 0$ to $N-1$) was constructed from the $2N$ observation equations

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} a_i - a_{i-1} = \dots \quad \text{weight} = (\sigma_{\eta_i}^2 + \sigma_{\eta_{i-1}}^2)^{-1} \\ a_i - a_{i-16} = \dots \quad \text{weight} = (\sigma_{\eta_i}^2 + \sigma_{\eta_{i-16}}^2)^{-1} \end{array} \right\} i \pmod{N} = 0 \text{ to } N-1 \quad (3)$$

in which the "input mean errors" σ_{η_i} were drawn (by means of a random number generator) from different distributions in the different experiments (Table 1, Fig. 1a-i). The "output mean errors" σ_{a_i} were computed from the diagonal elements of the pseudoinverted normal equations matrix (rank $N-1$). Finally q -averages were computed for both input and output errors and compared by the ratio

$$r(q) = \langle \sigma_a \rangle_q / \langle \sigma_{\eta} \rangle_q \quad q = -2, -1, 1, 2 \quad (4)$$

In experiment #0, all stars were given $\sigma_{\eta_i} = 1$, resulting in $\sigma_{a_i} = 1.054$ and hence $r(q) = 1.054$ for all q . Experiments #1-3 used symmetric distributions of σ_{η_i} with increasing dispersion; #4-6 used distributions with negative skewness and #7-9 with positive skewness. Resulting $r(q)$ -values are given in Table 1 and the input/output relations are plotted in Fig. 1 for experiments #1-9.

Table 1. $r(q)$ for 10 "mini-set" solutions with different symmetric and skew distributions of input mean errors ($\sigma_{\eta i}$). The dispersion of $\sigma_{\eta i}$ is indicated by the logarithmic range (column 3). The value q_0 satisfies $r(q_0) = 1.054$.

Exp.#	Fig.#	$\lg \frac{\sigma_{\eta \text{imax}}}{\sigma_{\eta \text{imin}}}$	$r(-2)$	$r(-1)$	$r(1)$	$r(2)$	q_0	Remark
0	-	0.00	1.054	1.054	1.054	1.054	-	
1	1-a	0.22	1.089	1.076	1.052	1.041	0.80	} symmetric distr.
2	1-b	0.45	1.192	1.142	1.048	1.010	0.86	
3	1-c	1.83	6.148	2.646	1.064	0.931	1.07	
4	1-d	0.51	1.225	1.159	1.062	1.029	1.22	} negative skewness
5	1-e	0.89	1.719	1.350	1.064	1.012	1.18	
6	1-f	1.22	2.437	1.556	1.066	1.012	1.21	
7	1-g	0.40	1.152	1.120	1.055	1.024	1.01	} positive skewness
8	1-h	0.53	1.229	1.171	1.060	1.014	1.13	
9	1-i	0.99	1.479	1.285	1.022	0.940	0.73	

It is seen that $r(1)$ is almost the same for all experiments, while the other q -values give much greater variations. This can also be seen by computing for each experiment the q -value (q_0) that would give the same r as in experiment #0, i.e. $r(q_0) = 1.054$. To the nearest integer we always have $q_0 = 1$. Several more experiments indicate that the deviations from $q_0 = 1$ in Table 1 are mostly due to statistical fluctuations. No clear trend can be seen depending on the dispersion or skewness of input mean errors.

The preference of $q = 1$ in these experiments is probably not a peculiarity of the system of equations (3), but more likely a rather general result. It should be realised that it is not a property of the arithmetic mean as such, but depends on the choice of the m.e. (s.d.) as precision measure. E.g. if the variance was taken as precision measure, then the $\frac{1}{2}$ -average would be the proper one to use.

This result ought to be tested on a full-scale set simulation, but for the present we accept $q = 1$ as the most appropriate average. In the following the operator $\langle \rangle$ always denotes the arithmetic mean.

FIGURE 1-a to 1-c. Abscissa (output) m.e. versus σ_{η_i} (input m.e.) for experiments #1 to 3. Note the different scales!

FIGURE 1-d to 1-f. Experiments #4 to 6 (negative skewness).

FIGURE 1-g to 1-i. Experiments #7 to 9 (positive skewness).

3. The set reduction formula

The proposed formula is

$$\sigma_{ai} = H \left[(1-h) \langle \sigma_{\eta} \rangle \langle n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle + h \sigma_{\eta i} n_i^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad (5)$$

depending on the two dimensionless numbers H and h . The first one, $H \geq 1$, measures the "slackness" (as opposed to "rigidity") of the overall solution; it may be determined from the average relation

$$\langle \sigma_a \rangle = H \langle \sigma_{\eta} \rangle \langle n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle \quad (6)$$

The second number, $0 \leq h \leq 1$, measures the "pliancy" of the solution, or its ability to adjust the output precision according to the input precision. It may be determined from

$$\frac{\sigma_{ai}}{\langle \sigma_a \rangle} - 1 = h \left[\frac{\sigma_{\eta i} n_i^{-\frac{1}{2}}}{\langle \sigma_{\eta} \rangle \langle n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle} - 1 \right] \quad (7)$$

A preliminary calibration of H and h can be obtained from the Copenhagen set simulation M-4, for which some details have been reported by Petersen, Byrnak and Poder (1982-08-07). The analysis is summarised in Table 2. The 2205 stars (excluding the origin star) were grouped in two different ways: first according to abscissa (top half of Table 2), then according to magnitude (bottom half). The abscissa origin in this set coincides with an anti-node of the scanning, so a larger number of stars is observed around abscissa 0 and 180° than at the nodes, 90° and 270°. From this point of view, the abscissa intervals 0-30°, 150-180°, 180-210°, and 330-360° are equivalent and therefore lumped together in Table 2 on the line "0-30°", and similarly for the other intervals. The abscissa grouping corresponds mainly to a variation of $n_i^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ (while $\sigma_{\eta i}$ is, on the average, the same in each interval), while the magnitude grouping gives different $\sigma_{\eta i}$ (but roughly the same $n_i^{-\frac{1}{2}}$) in the different intervals.

Column 3 in Table 2, σ_{a0} , contains the average abscissa mean error of respective group, as computed from the inverse normal equations matrix (Petersen et al., second table on p. 3). The average mean error $\langle \sigma_{a0} \rangle = 1.77$ mas is however inconsistent with the actual standard deviation of abscissa residuals, which is 1.4 mas (Petersen et al., first table on p. 3). The latter value is clearly the correct measure of the overall abscissa precision ($\langle \sigma_a \rangle = 1.4$ mas),

Table 2. Analysis of Copenhagen set simulation M-4. (Unit: 1 mas)

Group	N	σ_{a0}	σ_a	σ_η	$n^{-\frac{1}{2}}$	$\sigma_\eta \cdot n^{-\frac{1}{2}}$
0 - 30°	1080	1.85	1.490	4.663	0.1894	0.8832
30 - 60°	828	1.75	1.364	4.663	0.1659	0.7736
60 - 90°	297	1.60	1.168	4.663	0.0993	0.4630
average	2205	1.779	1.399	4.663	0.1684	0.7854
V < 6	105	1.69	1.296	3.677	0.1684	0.6192
6 - 7	227	1.72	1.335	4.003	0.1684	0.6741
7 - 8	628	1.73	1.347	4.368	0.1684	0.7356
8 - 8.7	1245	1.81	1.449	5.016	0.1684	0.8447
average	2205	1.772	1.401	4.663	0.1684	0.7853

and we believe that the higher value from the covariance matrix is due to the method of fixing the abscissa origin by means of a single star with postulated abscissa. If this interpretation is correct, the covariance matrix actually gives the mean errors of the abscissa differences w.r.t. the origin star. Neglecting the statistical correlations, the variances of "absolute" abscissae are then obtained by subtracting a constant "origin variance" from the diagonal elements of the covariance matrix. The corrected mean errors from

$$\sigma_a^2 = \sigma_{a0}^2 - (1.085 \text{ mas})^2 \quad (8)$$

are given in Column 4. The value 1.085 mas was chosen so that the resulting average abscissa m.e. is 1.40 mas.

Column 5 contains the average mean error per star per frame in the various groups. This depends on the magnitude (V) and was computed as follows (the actual values used in the Copenhagen simulation were not recorded). The 12 h set contains 21600 frames ($T_4 = 2$ s), of which only 19684 were retained (having ≥ 2 stars). 90282 observations were made, which makes on the average 4.587 stars per (retained) frame. In a frame with $m \geq 2$ stars, the observing time was partitioned in proportion to

$$\sigma_\eta(V, 1s) = \left[3.8 + 48500(1 + 100/f)/f \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ mas} \quad (9)$$

with

$$f = 4000 \cdot 10^{-0.4(V-9)} \quad (10)$$

With m stars in a frame, with magnitudes $V_1, V_2, \dots, V_m$, we get

$$\sigma_{\eta j} = \sigma_{\eta}^{\frac{1}{2}}(V_j, 1s) \left[\sum_{k=1}^m \sigma_{\eta}(V_k, 1s)/T_4 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (11)$$

To get the average σ_{η} as function of V we simulated some 1000 frames with $m = 2$ to 10 stars randomly drawn from the four magnitude groups in Table 2. For simplicity, a mean magnitude of $V = 5.3, 6.6, 7.6$ and 8.4 was assumed for all stars in a group (note that the median magnitude of real stars between V and $V+1$ is $V+0.62$). The m -values followed a truncated Poisson distribution forced to the mean value $\langle m \rangle = 4.587$ as in the Copenhagen set. The σ_{η} -values given in Column 5 yield the overall average $\langle \sigma_{\eta} \rangle = 4.663$ mas (cf. Petersen et al.: "a mean error on the observations of 0.005 arc-seconds").

The values $\eta^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ in Column 6 were computed from the assumption that each abscissa interval receives the same number of observations, i.e. $90282/3 = 30094$, but distributed over different numbers of stars. The average $\langle \eta^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle = 0.1684$ is in fair agreement with the theoretical value 0.1582 when the latter is corrected for missing observations (estimated to some 15 %).

From the last column of Table 2 and Eqn (6) we find

$$H = 1.78 \quad (12)$$

Least-squares determination of h in (7), giving equal weight to the seven groups in Table 2, yields

$$h = 0.40 \quad (13)$$

For the three abscissa groups only, we get $h = 0.42$, while the four magnitude groups give $h = 0.37$. Figure 2 shows the seven points together with the relation (5) with H and h according to (12) - (13).

The determination of h from the set simulation is rather sensitive to the correction for the origin variance, Eqn (8). To avoid this complication and uncertainty in future simulations, one should compute the standard deviations of the residuals for each magnitude and abscissa interval separately. The determination of H is on the other hand not affected by this problem.

FIGURE 2. Abscissa m.e. versus observation m.e. scaled by number of observations. Circles = results for abscissa groups; crosses = results for magnitude groups (Table 2). Line = fitted relation (5) with $H = 1.78$, $h = 0.40$.

4. Coefficients of improvement

The new COI (K_{λ} , K_{β} , $K_{\mu\lambda}$, $K_{\mu\beta}$, K_{Π}) for star number i are defined by

$$\sigma_{\lambda i} \cos \beta_i = K_{\lambda i} \langle \sigma_{ai} \rangle \quad \text{etc} \quad (14)$$

where $\langle \sigma_{ai} \rangle$ is the abscissa error of the star under average conditions, i.e. in particular $n_i^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \langle n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle$:

$$\langle \sigma_{ai} \rangle = H \langle n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle \left[(1-h) \langle \sigma_{\eta} \rangle + h \sigma_{\eta i} \right] \quad (15)$$

Note that the actual $n_i^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ is different in each set, and their mean value (for this particular star) over the mission is not necessarily $\langle n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle$. (E.g. a star at $\beta \approx \pm(90^\circ - \xi)$ is preferentially observed at scanning nodes which may give a 20% lower mean value of $n_i^{-\frac{1}{2}}$.)

Eqn (5) can now be written

$$\sigma_{ai} = \langle \sigma_{ai} \rangle \left[(1 - p_i) + p_i \frac{n_i^{-\frac{1}{2}}}{\langle n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle} \right] \quad (16)$$

where

$$p_i = \frac{h \sigma_{\eta i}}{(1 - h) \langle \sigma_{\eta} \rangle + h \sigma_{\eta i}} \quad (17)$$

in the range $0 \leq p_i \leq 1$ measures the sensitivity of σ_{ai} to an increased n_i . It is seen that p_i increases with $\sigma_{\eta i}$, i.e. with increasing magnitude. For a faint star it is thus possible to improve the abscissa m.e. by increasing the number of observations, but for a bright star this may not be possible (depending on h).

Assuming that the star is observed in every possible frame, the number of observations (in a given set) is clearly proportional to the number of great-circle scans across the star, n_{si} :

$$n_i = \frac{2\phi_\ell}{vT_4} n_{si} = 16.875 n_{si} \quad (18)$$

in the nominal case ($\phi_\ell = 0.9$ deg, $v = 180$ as/s, $T_4 = 2.13$ s). The new COI are thus computed by forming only one observation equation per set (instead of n_{si} equations for the old COI) and giving it the statistical weight

$$w(p_i, n_{si}) = \left[(1 - p_i) + p_i \frac{n_{si}^{-\frac{1}{2}}}{\langle n_s^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle} \right]^{-2} \quad (19)$$

$K_{\lambda i}$ etc are then obtained as the square roots of the diagonal elements of the inverse normal equations matrix (since $w = 1$ corresponds to $\sigma_{ai} = \langle \sigma_{ai} \rangle$). The number $\langle n_s^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle$ in (19) may be computed from the theoretical distribution of n_s , depending on Φ_t , the speed of precession $|\dot{z}|$, and the duration of a set (12 h). For uniform revolving scanning with $\xi = 43$ deg and $K = 6.4$ we have $|\dot{z}| = 0.18403$ deg/h (Lindgren, 1982-06-02) from which we derive

$$\langle n_s^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle = 0.6907 \quad (20)$$

(Remark: the area covered by the set is 745.76 deg^2 , yielding $\langle n_s \rangle = 2.6067$.)

FIGURE 3-a. Coefficients of improvement in longitude ($\Delta\lambda \cos \beta$) versus latitude, for $p = 0$ (bright star limit; top) and $p = 1$ (faint star limit; bottom).

Assumptions: $T = 2.5$ yr, $\xi = 43^\circ$, $K = 6.4$, $R = 12$ rpd, $\phi_t = 0.9^\circ$, "set" = 12 h

FIGURE 3-b. Same as Fig. 3-a but for the latitude component ($\Delta\beta$).

FIGURE 3-c. Same as Fig. 3-a but for the parallax (Π).

FIGURE 4. Top: NSET = number of sets in which a star is observed, versus latitude. Bottom: NGCS = number of great-circle scans across the star (2.5 yr, no dead time). Note difference in vertical scale.

It is seen that the new COI depend not only on position (λ_1, β_1) but also on p_i , i.e. on the stellar magnitude (or rather the ratio $\sigma_{\eta i}/\langle\sigma_{\eta}\rangle$).

For $p = 0, 0.5$, and 1 , the COI were computed at 320 test points on the sky. Results for $p = 0$ and 1 are shown in Fig. 3-a to 3-c. The results for the proper motion components are not shown because

$$K_{\mu\lambda}/K_{\lambda} \approx K_{\mu\beta}/K_{\beta} \approx 1.40 \text{ yr}^{-1} \quad (21)$$

for all stars independent of p . [The theoretical ratio is $12^{1/2}/(2.5 \text{ yr}) = 1.386 \text{ yr}^{-1}$.] Average values for the whole sky are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Coefficients of improvement (sky averages) as functions of p .

p	K_{λ}	K_{β}	$K_{\mu\lambda}$	$K_{\mu\beta}$	K_{Π}
0.0	0.302	0.246	0.421	0.345	0.362
0.5	0.297	0.240	0.413	0.340	0.360
1.0	0.282	0.227	0.394	0.326	0.349
$K_{\cdot}^0 =$	0.301	0.244	0.420	0.346	0.367

A reasonable fit to the tabulated values is

$$K_{\cdot} = K_{\cdot}^0 (1 - 0.06 p^2) \quad (22)$$

with $K_{\cdot}^0$ from the bottom line of Table 3.

Figure 4 shows the number of sets per star (NSET) and the number of great-circle scans per star (NGCS). The average numbers are

$$\langle\text{NSET}\rangle = 33.25 \quad \langle\text{NGCS}\rangle = 86.39 \quad \begin{matrix} (81 \text{ } \mu\text{m } R=11.5) \\ (50-200) \end{matrix} \quad (23)$$

excluding dead time of course.

5. Accuracy estimates

Table 4 summarises the accuracy estimates under the assumption that all stars are of colour $B-V = 0.5$. The first three lines give the magnitude intervals, the mean magnitudes and the number of stars in each interval.

Line 4 gives the variance of "photon-noise related error sources" for 1 s integration time, interpolated from MATRA's Figure 3.3.3/10 (p. 178 in E21-HIP-00767, Nov. 1982). This includes background, straylight, dark current, third harmonic, and IFOV piloting errors.

Line 5 shows the mean allocated time per star per frame (2.13 s). These times are in proportion to the "observing time per star" in ITT I-A, p. 40, and normalised to an overall average of 0.5432 s, corresponding to 3.927 stars per frame. This assumes that the full longitudinal FOV ($\Phi_\ell = 0.9$ deg) can be used. Line 6 gives the effective mean time per star per frame after correction for sample loss due to IFOV repositioning. According to E26-HIP-00166, p. 54, the effect of one lost sample on a full modulation period (8 samples) is to increase the variance by the factor 1.35. Thus the equivalent time loss per lost sample is $8 - 8/1.35 = 2.074$ samples, or 0.028 s per frame if there are 16 interlacing periods. Then

$$\bar{\tau}_e = \bar{\tau} - 0.028 \text{ s} \quad (24)$$

The resulting variance of all photon-noise related error sources is shown on Line 7, viz.

$$\sigma_{\eta\text{ph}}^2(\bar{B}, 0.5, \bar{\tau}_e) = \bar{\tau}_e^{-1} \sigma_{\eta\text{ph}}^2(\bar{B}, 0.5, 1 \text{ s}) \quad (25)$$

The total variance at frame level is set to

$$\sigma_\eta^2(\bar{B}, 0.5, \bar{\tau}_e) = \sigma_{\eta\text{ph}}^2(\bar{B}, 0.5, \bar{\tau}_e) + 10 \text{ mas}^2 \quad (26)$$

The contribution of 10 mas^2 consists of grid errors (6 mas^2), attitude errors about the optical axes (0.1 as rms $\Rightarrow 2 \text{ mas}^2$ at frame level) and other sources (2 mas^2). Resulting average mean error is $\langle \sigma_\eta \rangle = 13.65 \text{ mas}$, which with $\langle n^{-1/2} \rangle = 0.16814$ [Eqns (18) and (20)], $H = 1.78$ and $h = 0.40$ gives Line 10:

$$\sigma_{a1} = 2.451 + 0.1197 \sigma_\eta \quad (27)$$

Line 11 gives σ_{a2} from

$$\sigma_{a2}^2 = \sigma_{a1}^2 + 1 \text{ mas}^2 \quad (28)$$

accounting for the abscissa zero point uncertainty ($3.5 \text{ mas}/\sqrt{20} = 0.8 \text{ mas}$ for 20 PRS stars) and basic angle variations ($\leq 0.6 \text{ mas}$).

Lines 12 and 13 contain the degradation factors due to veiling glare and dead time (occultations). The former factors (F_{VG}) are derived in the Appendix; the latter are constant $F_{DT} = 1.078$ corresponding to 14 % dead time. Application of these factors give the final abscissa mean errors (σ_a) in Line 14.

The numbers p in Line 15 are obtained from (17) with $h = 0.40$ and $\langle \sigma_\eta \rangle = 13.65 \text{ mas}$. They are used in (22) to compute the COI, which finally give the astrometric m.e. in Lines 16 - 20.

These estimates are for stars of colour $B-V = 0.5$. For other colours one must take into account the different count rates and chromaticity of the instrument. The colour effects on count rate, signal modulation etc can be eliminated by considering a fixed "HIPPARCOS magnitude"

$$H \approx B - 0.6(B-V) \quad (29)$$

making $\sigma_{\eta\text{ph}}^2$ independent of $B-V$ (cf. MATRA's Fig. 3.3.3/10, p. 178 in E21-HIP-00767). The chromaticity is taken into account by adding to the abscissa variance

$$C_c^2 + 4C_v^2 = 8.5 \text{ mas}^2 \quad (B-V = -0.25 \text{ or } 1.25) \quad (30)$$

thus increasing the astrometric m.e. at $H = 8.7$ by a factor 1.20 and at $H = 11.7$ by 1.03. Eqn (30) is motivated by that the constant chromaticity ($C_c = 2.1 \text{ mas}$ according to MACP's letter of 1983-01-07) propagates to the astrometric parameters factored by numbers $\sim \text{COI}$, while a varying part ($C_v = 1 \text{ mas}$) propagates with factors $\sim 2 \times \text{COI}$ (Lindgren, 1982-11-01).

TABLE 4

(1)	B	- 6	6 - 7	7 - 8	8 - 9	9.0	9 - 10	10 - 11	11 - 12	12.0	12 - 13	MEAN
(2)	$\bar{B}$	5.4	6.6	7.6	8.6	9.0	9.5	10.5	11.5	12.0	12.5	--
(3)	N	3000	5400	14800	40800	--	16000	12000	6000	--	2000	--
(4)	$\sigma_{\eta\text{ph}}^2(\bar{B}, .5, 1\text{s})$	2.03	5.38	14.8	42.3	57.9	104	336	961	1918	5817	--
(5)	$\bar{\tau}$	0.226	0.259	0.326	0.443	0.511	0.610	0.828	1.112	1.287	1.489	0.543
(6)	$\bar{\tau}_e$	0.198	0.231	0.298	0.415	0.483	0.582	0.800	1.084	1.295	1.461	0.515
(7)	$\sigma_{\eta\text{ph}}^2(\bar{B}, .5, \bar{\tau}_e)$	10.3	23.3	49.7	102	120	179	420	887	1523	3982	--
(8)	$\sigma_{\eta}^2(\bar{B}, .5, \bar{\tau}_e)$	20.3	33.3	59.7	112	130	189	430	897	1533	3992	--
(9)	$\sigma_{\eta}(\bar{B}, .5, \bar{\tau}_e)$	4.51	5.77	7.73	10.6	11.4	13.7	20.7	29.9	39.2	63.2	13.65
(10)	σ_{a1}	2.99	3.14	3.38	3.72	3.82	4.09	4.93	6.03	7.14	10.0	4.09
(11)	σ_{a2}	3.15	3.30	3.52	3.85	3.94	4.21	5.03	6.03	7.21	10.1	4.21
(12)	F_{VG}	1.002	1.004	1.008	1.016	1.021	1.028	1.049	1.083	1.091	1.100	1.025
(13)	F_{DT}	1.078	1.078	1.078	1.078	1.078	1.078	1.078	1.078	1.078	1.078	1.078
(14)	σ_a	3.40	3.57	3.82	4.22	4.34	4.67	5.69	7.04	8.48	12.0	4.68
(15)	P	0.181	0.220	0.274	0.341	0.358	0.401	0.503	0.594	0.657	0.755	0.372
(16)	σ_{λ}	1.02	1.07	1.14	1.26	1.30	1.39	1.69	2.07	2.49	3.49	1.39
(17)	σ_{β}	0.83	0.87	0.93	1.02	1.05	1.13	1.37	1.68	2.01	2.82	1.13
(18)	$\sigma_{\mu\lambda}$	1.43	1.50	1.60	1.76	1.81	1.94	2.36	2.89	3.47	4.86	1.94
(19)	$\sigma_{\mu\beta}$	1.17	1.23	1.32	1.45	1.49	1.60	1.94	2.38	2.86	4.00	1.60
(20)	σ_{Π}	1.25	1.31	1.40	1.54	1.58	1.70	2.06	2.53	3.03	4.25	1.70

APPENDIX

Degradation factor due to veiling glare

The factor F_{VG} is derived here under the assumption that an observation is either rejected, namely when it is suspected to be significantly disturbed by veiling glare (VG), or accepted and uncorrected. Thus there are two kinds of contribution to F_{VG} : due to dead time (rejected observations) and due to an increased variance at frame level (from significant but uncorrected perturbations).

Let $m(r)$ be the IFOV damping profile in magnitudes, i.e. $m(0) = 0$ and $m(r) > 0$ for $r > 0$. If B is the magnitude of the observed star and B' that of the disturbing star at distance r from the former, the rms bias is

$$b_{rms} \approx (100 \text{ mas}) \cdot 10^{-0.4[B' - B + m(r)]} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

[cf. Lindegren, 1982-06-15, Eqn (16)]. If this goes uncorrected, the net effect on the frame variance is

$$\sigma_{\eta\text{total}}^2 = \sigma_{\eta}^2 + M b_{rms}^2 \quad (\text{A.2})$$

since it is coherent over the $M \sim 8$ frames of a FOV crossing. The ability to detect VG during processing of the frames depends on the ratio b_{rms}/σ_{η} .

Very schematically we may distinguish three cases:

A. Insignificant VG. The criterion may be

$$b_{rms} \leq 0.1 \sigma_{\eta} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

corresponding to $\sigma_{\eta\text{total}} \leq 1.04 \sigma_{\eta}$.

B. Significant but undetectable VG. The criterion is

$$0.1 \sigma_{\eta} < b_{rms} \leq \sigma_{\eta} \quad \text{and} \quad B' > 10 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

C. Significant and detectable VG. This is the case with

$$b_{rms} > \sigma_{\eta} \quad \text{or} \quad \left[b_{rms} > 0.1 \sigma_{\eta} \quad \text{and} \quad B' \leq 10 \right] \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Note that VG is detectable either if $b_{\text{rms}} > \sigma_{\eta}$ or if $B' \leq 10$. The first condition corresponds roughly to a 3σ -limit on the level of a FOV passage, while the second condition is motivated by the relative completeness of star catalogues (CSI) down to $B \approx 10$. Figure A-1 shows the corresponding regions A, B, C in the B' - r diagram for a $B = 12$ star.

Defining r_1 , r_2 , and r_3 as in the figure ($r_3 = 2000$ as is set by the FOV size), we obtain the expected number of disturbing stars in regions B and C,

$$n_B = n_2 - n_1 \quad n_C = n_3 - n_1 \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where

$$n_1 = \int_0^{r_1} 2\bar{N} \left[B + 2.5 \lg \{ \sigma_{\eta} / 100 \text{ mas} \} - m(r) \right] 2\pi r dr \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$n_2 = \int_0^{r_2} 2\bar{N} \left[B + 2.5 \lg \{ 0.1 \sigma_{\eta} / 100 \text{ mas} \} - m(r) \right] 2\pi r dr \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$n_3 = \int_{r_2}^{r_3} 2\bar{N} \left[B + 2.5 \lg \{ 0.1 \sigma_{\eta} / 100 \text{ mas} \} - m(r) \right] 2\pi r dr \quad (\text{A.9})$$

and $\bar{N}(B')$ is the density of stars brighter than B' . The probability of Case A is now

$$f_C = 1 - \exp(-n_C) \quad (\text{A.10})$$

and of Case B,

$$f_B = \exp(-n_C) \left[1 - \exp(-n_B) \right] \quad (\text{A.11})$$

The factor $\exp(-n_C)$ in (A.11) is the probability that there is no star in region C, which is a necessary condition for Case B. The probability of Case A is consequently

$$f_A = 1 - f_B - f_C = \exp(-n_B - n_C) \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Since the observation is rejected in Case C only, the fractional dead time due to VG is f_C . During the time fraction f_A the observation variance per frame

is σ_{η}^2 , while during time fraction f_B it is $\sigma_{\eta\text{total}}^2 = 1.08\sigma_{\eta}^2$ to $9\sigma_{\eta}^2$. For simplicity let us put $\sigma_{\eta\text{total}}^2 = F\sigma_{\eta}^2$ in Case B, with a constant $F \sim 2$. The overall degradation factor is then

$$F_{VG} = \frac{(f_A + Ff_B)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{f_A + f_B} \tag{A.13}$$

Table A-1 shows some results obtained with the IFOV profile by Bonnefoy (letter of 1982-12-23) and the mean star density function (Lindgren, 1982-11-14)

$$\bar{N}(B) = \text{dex}(-4.06 + 0.525B - 0.005B^2) \text{ deg}^{-2} \tag{A.14}$$

Note that physical companion stars (double and multiple stars) are not included here.

Table A-1. Fraction of undisturbed observation (f_A), undetectably disturbed (f_B) and detectably disturbed (f_C).

B	5.4	6.6	7.6	8.6	9.5	10.5	11.5	12.5	mean
f_A	.9969	.9917	.9837	.9685	.9452	.9056	.8415	.8126	.9508
f_B	.0023	.0068	.0128	.0230	.0387	.0644	.1041	.1212	.0343
f_C	.0008	.0015	.0035	.0085	.0161	.0300	.0544	.0662	.0149
F_{VG}	1.002	1.004	1.008	1.016	1.028	1.049	1.083	1.100	1.025

FIGURE A-1. Regions corresponding to the three cases A, B, C for observation of a $B = 12$ star. B' = magnitude of disturbing star at distance r .